

ИЖТИМОЙ ФАНЛАРНИ ЎҚИТИЛИШИДА АХБОРОТ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРДАН ФЙДАЛАНИШНИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада юртимизда таълим-тарбия жараёнига ахборот коммуникация технологияларини жорий этиш орқали бир қанча қулайликлар яратилгани ва ўсиб, улғайиб келаётган ёш авлодни баркамол қилиб тарбиялашда янги педагогик технологиялардан ўз вақтида ва унумли фойдаланишда ахборот технологияларинг истиқболли томонлари ёритиб берилган.

Аннотация: В данной статье внедрение информационно-коммуникационных технологий в образовательный процесс в нашей стране создало ряд удобств и перспективных сторон информационных технологий в своевременном и эффективном использовании новых педагогических технологий в воспитании подрастающей молодежи поколение.

Abstract: In this article, the introduction of information and communication technologies to the educational process in our country has created a number of conveniences and the promising aspects of information technologies in the timely and effective use of new pedagogical technologies in the education of the growing young generation.

Калит сўзи: ахборот, таълим, тарбия, педагогик технология, ахборот технология, интернет.

Ключевое слово: информация, образование, воспитание, педагогические технологии, информационные технологии, интернет.

Key word: information, education, education, pedagogical technology, information technology, internet.

It is known that the introduction of new pedagogical and information communication technologies into the educational system is one of the important issues of today. A number of conveniences are created by introducing information and communication technologies to the educational process. So, with the development of science and technology in our country, the possibility of obtaining information is increasing. It is necessary to make effective use of scientific and technical achievements in the delivery of information to students within the scope of demand. The promising aspects of the timely and effective use of new pedagogical technologies in the proper education of the growing young generation are being demonstrated.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 of January 28, 2022 on the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026¹, The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Information"², Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 21, 2012 "On measures for the further introduction and development of modern

¹ PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>

² Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Information" December 11, 2003, <https://lex.uz/docs/83472?ONDATE=30.03.2021%2000>

information and communication technologies"³, Decisions of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 27, 2013 "On measures to further develop the national information and communication system"⁴, Decree No. PF-5349 dated February 19, 2018 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the field of information technologies and communications"⁵. The above-mentioned goal requires raising the educational process to higher levels by increasing the efficiency of using information and communication technologies, Internet and multimedia resources in the public education system.

In line with progress, the treasure of knowledge is getting richer, and the intellectual potential of young people is increasing. There is no need to explain that a real information society was created in the process of information. Accordingly, the number of media technologies is growing. Image, sound and text are literally combined, and audiovisual culture is being improved in its own way. Now, its widespread use in the field of education has become the demand of the times. In today's so-called "Information and Globalization Age", it is important to provide the educational process with advanced pedagogical technologies in order to achieve this goal.

In today's fast-paced processes, every person is showing his involvement in the changes taking place in the society (in the world). In this regard, it means that new pedagogical technologies, innovations, new pedagogical-psychological concepts, content and essence of interactive methods, specific features and methods of application in teaching processes should be studied and researched more deeply.

In the course of training, it is important to develop the basic competencies of working with information from the audience.

Information competence - being able to use available information sources (internet, television, radio (audio-video recording), telephone, computer, e-mail, etc.).

In the educational system, using modern innovative technologies, it is possible to collect, store, process information resources, and use special software tools to create electronic and virtual libraries, multimedia electronic educational literature, lectures, and various animation works.

Computer networks and information technologies have created opportunities for the educational system to quickly obtain the necessary information. Instant access to the world's information resources through the Internet global computer network is a clear proof of this.

As information is received through fast Internet, most of its users are young people. Most of them are regular users of social sites. "Organizing the channels of state bodies and organizations on social networks on the Internet (Facebook, Telegram, Twitter, Youtube, Mytube.uz, etc.) and placing legal propaganda materials on these channels, based on the directions of industry activities, using web technologies widely."

Also, it is most important for our youth to express their involvement and attitude to our current reforms during their activities. In this regard, our President Sh. M. Large-scale reforms are being carried out on the study of Mirziyoyev's decree No. 6 of May 11, 2022 "On

³ Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the further introduction and development of modern information and communication technologies", No. PQ-1730 dated 21.03.2012. People's Word newspaper, March 22, 2012

⁴ Decision PQ-1989 of June 27, 2013 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further develop the national information and communication system of the Republic of Uzbekistan". <https://lex.uz/docs/2246001?ONDATE=07.10.2013>

⁵ Decree No. PF-5653 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of February 2, 2018 "On additional measures for the further development of the information sector and mass communications", Xalq sozi newspaper, February 5, 2018, No. 24 (7254)

the approval of the state program on the approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026" (PF-134)⁶.

In our country, a number of decisions, decrees and orders of the President were issued in order to create the necessary conditions for comprehensively satisfying the information needs of students of all educational institutions, as well as to develop information resources that provide education and knowledge in the national segment of the Internet. Today, we recommend the following as examples of useful sites that our youth should use: www.Uzedu.uz, www.ZiyoNet.uz, www.Kitob.uz, www.Lex.uz, www.Norma.uz, uza.uz and other sites.

Today, electronic textbooks provide an opportunity to use information and educational technologies in teaching in schools. Also, the effective organization of the teaching process by means of electronic resources ensures the achievement of educational goals. It should also be noted that if the teaching process is not well organized, advanced pedagogical and information technologies will not be effective enough.

In short, it is possible to increase the students' vocabulary, listen to different texts, establish a mutual conversation, and organize performances using ICT in the classes. It is important to use ICT in the training to attract the attention of all the audience at the same time and to explain the content of the training. Because, with the help of ICT, in addition to influencing the student both audially and visually, there are many opportunities to form the skills of free, creative thinking and working alone or in cooperation.

⁶ No. PF-134 dated May 11, 2022 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026". <https://lex.uz/docs/6008663>

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5. Decree No. PF-5653 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2019 "On additional measures for the further development of the information sector and mass communications", Xalq sozi newspaper, February 5, 2019, No. 24 (7254)
6. No. PF-134 dated May 11, 2022 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026". <https://lex.uz/docs/6008663>
7. Holiday greetings of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev to the teachers and coaches of Uzbekistan. <https://www.gazeta.uz/uz/2022/09/30/president/>

